

The Intangibles of Heritage: Concept, Recording, Safeguarding

11:00

Welcome and Opening Remarks

Erasmus Mundus Master TPTI & HERITAS – UNESCO Chair, University of Évora

11:05 – 11:30 **Transforming, not saving. The Archive, the Repertoire and the World.**

MARC JACOBS - University of Antwerp, UNESCO Chairholder on Critical Heritage Studies and the Safeguarding of Intangible Heritage - Vrije Universiteit Brussel

11:30 – 11:45 **The MEMORIAMEDIA project – recording and safeguarding ICH**

FILOMENA SOUSA - IF researcher, Memória Imaterial, Portugal

11:45 – 12:00 **Social cohesion, migrations and ICH: experimenting to mix them**

FILIPE THEMUDO BARATA - CIDEHUS, UNESCO Chairholder on Intangible Heritage and Traditional Know - How: Linking Heritage - University of Évora

12:00 – 12:15 **Heritage literacy: a possible knowledge management model of (intangible) heritage**

DARKO BABIĆ - University of Zagreb

12:15 – 12:30 **ICH and Museums: Exploring interactions**

ANA CARVALHO - CIDEHUS, University of Évora

12:30 – 12:45 **Intangible Cultural Heritage: Continuity and Complexities**

MONALISA MAHARJAN - CIDEHUS, University of Évora

12: 45 -12:55 **Questions**

13:00

Closing speech

Erasmus Mundus Master TPTI - CIDEHUS, University of Évora

Moderator:

SARA ALBINO - CIDEHUS, University of Évora

